

REVIEW ON VARIOUS MEDICINAL PLANTS WITH HEPATOPROTECTIVE ACTIVITY

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Abstract

The liver is one of the most important organs in the body, performing a fundamental role in the regulation of diverse processes, among which the metabolism, secretion, storage, and detoxification of endogenous and exogenous substances are prominent. Due to these functions, hepatic diseases continue to be among the main threats to public health, and they remain problems throughout the world. Despite enormous advances in modern medicine, there are no completely effective drugs that stimulate hepatic function, that offer complete protection of the organ, or that help to regenerate hepatic cells. Thus, it is necessary to identify pharmaceutical alternatives for the treatment of liver diseases, with the aim of these alternatives being more effective and less toxic. The use of some plants and the consumption of different fruits have played basic roles in human health care, and diverse scientific investigations have indicated that, in those plants and fruits so identified, their beneficial effects can be attributed to the presence of chemical compounds that are called phytochemicals. The present review is aimed at compiling data on promising phytochemicals from hepatoprotective herbs.

Keywords: hepatoprotective herbs, liver, hepatic function

INTRODUCTION

The liver is the most important organ that plays an important role in maintaining various physiological processes in the body. It is involved in several vital functions, such as metabolism, secretion, and storage. It plays a central role in the detoxification and excretion of many exogenous and endogenous compounds. Hence, any injury to it or impairment of its function has grave implications for the health of the affected person. Every year, about 18,000 people are reported to die due to liver cirrhosis caused by hepatitis, although viral infection is one of the main causes for hepatic injury. It acts as a storage depot for proteins, glycogen, various vitamins, and metals. It also has a role in the regulation of blood volume by transferring the blood from the portal to the systemic circulation and its reticulo-endothelial system and participates in the immune mechanism. The human body identifies almost all drugs as foreign substances (i.e., xenobiotics) and subjects them to various chemical processes (such as metabolism) to make them suitable for elimination. This involves chemical transformations to reduce fat solubility and change biological activity [1]. Although almost all tissues in the body have some ability to metabolize chemicals, smooth endoplasmic reticulum in liver is the principal “metabolic clearing house” for both endogenous chemicals (e.g., cholesterol, steroid hormones, fatty acids, and proteins), and exogenous substances (e.g., drugs). The central role played by the liver in the clearance and transformation of chemicals also makes it susceptible to drug-induced injury [2].

Hepatitis is an inflammation of the liver and is characterized by the presence of inflammatory cells in the tissue of the organ. There are five main viruses, referred to as types A, B, C, D, and E. These five types are of the greatest concern because of the burden of illness and death. The condition can be self-limiting (healing on its own) or can progress to fibrosis (scarring) and cirrhosis. Hepatitis may occur with limited or no symptoms, but often leads to jaundice, anorexia (poor appetite), and malaise. Hepatitis is acute when it lasts less than 6 months and chronic when it persists for longer. Hepatic trouble, which includes parasites and viral infections; autoimmune diseases; and intoxication with various xenobiotics such as alcohol, herbal medicine, drugs, chlorinated solvents, peroxidized fatty acids, fungal toxins, industrial pollutants, and radioactive isotopes. In particular, types A and C lead to chronic disease in hundreds of millions of people and, together, are the most common cause of liver cirrhosis and cancer [3].

About 1 million deaths per year are attributed to viral hepatitis infection, that is, hepatitis B virus (HBV) and hepatitis C virus (HCV) taken together, which is the leading cause of liver cirrhosis and cancer, accounting for 78% of cases. Nearly 1 out of every 3 people in the world (approximately 2 million people) has been infected by HBV and HCV. On World Hepatitis Day, July 28, 2013, the World Health Organization (WHO) and its partners focused on the fact that although the burden of disease caused by viral hepatitis is growing, it remains largely ignored or unknown to many policymakers, health workers, and the public [4].

In India, The use of herbal products for the management of disease has a long history, starting with Ayurvedic management, and proceeding to the European and Chinese alternative systems of ancient medicines. Medicinal plants are significant sources of hepatoprotective drugs. According to one estimate, more than 700 mono- and polyherbal preparations in the form of decoction, tincture, and tablets have been used in various liver disorders. The 21st century has seen a paradigm shift toward therapeutic evaluation of herbal products in liver disease models by carefully synergizing the strengths of the traditional system of medicine with that of the modern concept of evidence-based therapeutical screening, authentication, and randomized placebo-controlled clinical trials to support clinical efficacy. A large number of plants and formulations have been claimed to show hepatoprotective activities. Around 160 active constituents from 101 plants are claimed to have post liver protecting activity. In India, quite eighty seven plants square measure used in 33 patented propitiatory multi-ingredient plant formulations [5].

In spite of the tremendous advances made, no important and safe hepatoprotective agents are obtainable in modern medicine Therefore, due importance has been given globally to develop primarily plant-based hepatoprotective medications that are effective against a range of liver disorders. A drug having helpful results on the liver is understood as a hepatoprotective drug. On the other hand, drugs having toxic effects on the liver are called hepatotoxic drugs. Clinical analysis has conjointly shown that herbals have real utility in the treatment of diseases. In the last 30 years, several hepatotoxins have been used commonly in d-galactosamine, carbon tetrachloride, acetaminophen, and thioacetamide, and more recently Concanavalin A (ConA) and lipopolysaccharide (LPS) has been developed. ConA and LPS do not reflect the clinical pattern of human disease, which indicates a great advantage in the study of cellular mechanisms involved in autoimmune liver disease. The galactosamine model is a highly selective hepatotoxin that causes liver damage similar to human viral

hepatitis via depletion of uridine nucleotides, which subsequently diminishes the synthesis of RNA and proteins.[6]

Galactosamine intoxication in rats disrupts the membrane permeability of the plasma membrane, causing leakage of the enzymes from the cell, which leads to the elevation of serum enzymes. Hence, a significant rise in the transaminase levels could be taken as an index of liver damage. Galactosamine has great liver specificity compared to other toxic groups, such as paracetamol, acetaminophen, and carbon tetrachloride because hepatocytes have high levels of galactokinase and galactose-1-uridylyltransferase, and galactosamine does not affect other organs. Galactosamine induces hepatotoxicity with spotty hepatocytes, necrosis, and marked portal and parenchymal infiltration.[7] Galactosamine also induces the depletion of uridine diphosphate (UDP) by increasing the production of UDP-sugar derivatives, which causes inhibition of RNA and protein synthesis, leading to cell membrane deterioration [8]. The current study is aimed toward assembling information-supported reported works on promising phytochemical from herbal plants that are tested in hepatotoxicity models. The review deals with fact-finding work done on herbals helpful in the treatment of liver ailments.

Hepatoprotective plants

Andrographis lineatanees

Hepatoprotective effect of *Andrographis lineata* (Acanthaceae) extracts in CCl₄- induced liver injury in rats. Male Wistar rats with chronic liver damage, induced by subcutaneous injection of 50% v/v CCl₄ in liquid paraffin at a dose of 3 mL/kg on alternate days for a period of 4 weeks, were treated with methanol and aqueous extracts of *A. lineata* orally at a dose of 845 mg/kg/day. The biochemical parameters such as serum glutamate oxaloacetate transaminase, serum glutamate pyruvate transaminase, serum bilirubin and alkaline phosphatase were estimated to assess the liver function. Histopathological examinations of liver tissue corroborated well with the biochemical changes. The activities of extracts were comparable to a standard drug [9].

***Azadirachta indica* (Neem)**

Effect of *A. indica* leaf (meliaceae) extract on serum enzyme levels (glutamate oxaloacetate transaminase, glutamate pyruvate transaminase, acid phosphatase and alkaline phosphatase) elevated by paracetamol in rats was studied with a view to observe any possible hepatoprotective effect of this plant. It is stipulated that the extract treated group was

protected from hepatic cell damage caused by paracetamol induction. The findings were further confirmed by histopathological study of liver. The antihepatotoxic action of picroliv seems likely due to an alteration in the biotransformation of the toxic substances resulting in decreased formation of reactive metabolites [10]

Careya arborea

The methanol extract of *Careya arborea* bark, (myrtaceae) was tested for antioxidant and hepatoprotective activity in Ehrlich ascites carcinoma (EAC) tumor-bearing mice. Tumor control animals inoculated with EAC showed a significant alteration in the levels of antioxidant and hepatoprotective parameters⁸. The extract treatment at 50, 100 and 200 mg/kg body weight doses given orally caused a significant reversal of these biochemical changes towards the normal in serum. Liver and kidney when compared to tumor control animals indicating the potent antioxidant and hepatoprotective nature of the standardized extract [11].

Cassia fistula (Amaltas)

Hepatoprotective activity of the n-heptane extract of *Cassia fistula* (Fabaceae) leaves was investigated by inducing hepatotoxicity with paracetamol in rats. The extract at a dose of 400 mg/kg body wt. exhibited orally, significant protective effect by lowering the serum levels of transaminases (SGOT and SGPT), bilirubin and alkaline phosphatase (ALP). The effects produced were comparable to that of a standard hepatoprotective agent [12]

Eclipta Alba (Bhringaraj)

The hepatoprotective effect of the ethanol/water (1:1) extract of *Eclipta Alba* (Asteraceae) was studied at subcellular levels in rats against (CCl₄)-induced hepatotoxicity. The loss of hepatic lysosomal acid phosphatase and alkaline phosphatase by (CCl₄) was significantly restored by *Eclipta Alba*. The study shows that hepatoprotective activity of *Eclipta Alba* is by regulating the levels of hepatic microsomal drug metabolising enzymes [13].

Fumaria indica (hauskn)

Fumaria indica (Fumariceae) were studied for their hepatoprotective activity against carbontetrachloride, paracetamol and rifampicin-induced hepatotoxicities in albino rats. The petroleum ether extract against carbonetrachloride, total aqueous extract against paracetamol and methanolic extract against rifampicin-induced hepatotoxicities showed similar reductions

in the elevated levels of some of the serum biochemical parameters in a manner similar that of silymarin indicating its potential as a hepatoprotective agent [14].

Morindacitrifolia L. (noni)

The hepatoprotective effects of Noni juice (TNJ) (Rubiaceae) against CCl₄-induced chronic liver damage in female Sprague Dawley (SD) rats. Histopathological examination revealed that liver sections from the TNJ + CCl₄ appeared similar to controls, whereas typical hepatic steatosis was observed in the placebo + CCl₄ group. Serum alkaline phosphatase (ALP), aspartate aminotransferase (AST), alanine transaminase (ALT), total cholesterol (TC), triglycerides (TG), low-density lipoprotein (LDL), and very low-density lipoprotein (VLDL) levels were increased in the placebo group compared with the TNJ group. In contrast, high-density lipoprotein (HDL) was increased in the TNJ group and decreased in the placebo group. Thus, TNJ juice appears to protect the liver from chronic exogenous CCl₄ exposures [15].

Phyllanthus amarus (Bhuiamala)

Ethanol extract of *Phyllanthus amarus* (euphorbiaceae), at (0.3g kg⁻¹ BW 0.2 ml⁻¹ day⁻¹) was given to all groups except control groups (gp. I and gp. V), after 30 min of aflatoxin administration. The entire study was carried out for 3 months and animals were sacrificed after an interval of 30 days till the completion of study. *Phyllanthus amarus* extract was found to show hepatoprotective effect by lowering down the content of thiobarbituric acid reactive substances (TBARS) and enhancing the reduced glutathione level and the activities of antioxidant enzymes, glutathione peroxidase (GPx), glutathione-S-transferase (GST), superoxide dismutase (SOD) and catalase (CAT) [16].

Phyllanthus emblica (amla)

Ethanol extract of *Phyllanthus emblica* Linn. (Euphorbiaceae) (PE) induced rat hepatic injury. PE (0.5 and 1 mg/ml) increased cell viability of rat primary cultured hepatocytes being treated with ethanol (96 µl/m) by increasing % MTT and decreasing the release of transaminase. Pretreatment of rats with PE at oral dose of 25, 50 and 75 mg/kg or SL (silymarin, a reference hepatoprotective agent) at 5 mg/kg, 4 h before ethanol lowered the ethanol induced levels of AST, ALT and IL1beta. The 75 mg/kg PE dose gave the best result similar to SL. Treatment of rats with PE (75 mg/kg/day) or SL (5 mg/kg/day) for 7 days after

21 days with ethanol (4 g/kg/day, p.o.) enhanced liver cell recovery by bringing the levels of AST, ALT, IL-1beta back to normal [17].

Polygala arvensis

Chloroform extract of leaves of *Polygala arvensis* (polygalaceae), in 0.3% carboxy methyl cellulose (CMC) was evaluated for hepatoprotective activity in Wistar albino rats by inducing hepatic injury with d-galactosamine (400 mg/kg). The chloroform extract of *Polygala arvensis* at an oral dose of 200 mg/kg and 400 mg/kg exhibited a significant [18].

***Pterocarpus santalinus* (Kanak champa)**

the aqueous (45 mg/ml) and ethanol (30 mg/ml) extracts of *Pterocarpus santalinus* (Fabaceae) stem bark in 1% gum tragacanth was administered orally for 14 days and the hepatoprotective activity studied in CCl₄ induced hepatic damage model. There was a significant increase in serum levels of bilirubin, alanine transaminase, aspartate transaminase and alkaline phosphatase with a decrease in total protein level, in the CCl₄ treated animals, reflecting liver injury. In the extracts treated animals there was a decrease in serum levels of the markers and significant increase in total protein, indicating the recovery of hepatic cells. Ethanol extract treated animal's revealed normal hepatic cords without any cellular necrosis and fatty infiltration [19].

***Pterospermum acerifolium* (Kanak champa)**

The hepatoprotective activity of the ethanol extract of the leaf of *Pterospermum acerifolium* (Sterculiaceae) was investigated in rats. Hepatotoxicity was induced in male Wistar rats by intraperitoneal injection of carbon tetrachloride (0.1 ml/kg/d p.o. for 14 d). Ethanol extract of *P. acerifolium* leaves were administered to the experimental rats (25 mg/kg/d p.o. for 14d). The Hepatoprotective effect of these extracts was evaluated by liver function biochemical parameters (total bilirubin, serum protein, alanine aminotransaminase, asparatate aminotransaminase and alkaline phosphates activites) and histopathological studies of liver. In ethanol extracttreated animals, the toxicity effect of carbon tetrachloride was controlled significantly by restoration of the levels of serum bilirubin and enzymes as compared to the normal and standard drug silymarin-treated groups [20].

Solanum nigrum (Makoi) and Cichorium intybus (Kasni)

The presence of plant extracts of *Solanum nigrum* (solanaceae) and *Cichorium intybus* (Asteraceae) in the reaction mixture containing calf thymus DNA and free radical generating system protect DNA against oxidative damage to its deoxyribose sugar moiety. The effect was dependent on the concentration of plant extracts. However, the effect of *Cichorium intybus* was much pronounced as compared to the effect of *Solanum nigrum*. These studies suggest that the observed hepatoprotective effect of these crude plant extracts may be due to their ability to suppress the oxidative degradation of DNA in the tissue debris [21].

Swertia Chirata (Chirayata)

Simultaneous treatments with *S. Chirata* (Gentianaceae). (in different doses, viz, 20, 50, and 100 mg/kg body wt daily) and (CCl₄) caused improvement at both biochemical and histopathological parameters compared to that of (CCl₄) treatment alone but it was most effective when *S. chirata* was administered in a moderate dose (50 mg/kg body wt) [22].

Wedeliacalendulacea L (Bhanra)

Hepatoprotective activity of the ethanolic-leaf extract of *W.calendulacea* (Asteraceae) (EEWC) was studied by estimating serum enzyme activities of aspartate aminotransferase (AST), alanine aminotransferase (ALT), alkaline phosphatase (ALP), protein and bilirubin. 4 The treatment with EEWC showed a dose-dependent reduction of CCl₄ induced elevated serum levels of enzyme activities with parallel increase in total protein and bilirubin, indicating the extract could preserve the normal functional status of the liver [23-24].

CONCLUSIONS

Herbal and traditional botanical products have been used since ancient times for the treatment of various disorders and diseases. Those herbal plants have been discussed that have been previously explored by various researchers for their hepatoprotective activities. Several medicinal plants exhibit not only hepatoprotective activities but also a wide range of anticancer, cardiatic, diuretic, antiarrhythmic, and other medicinal activities. New hepatoprotective plants are important for the discovery of drugs that are less costly, have fewer side effects, are more potent, and allow effective treatment developed for hepatoprotection and immune response. Herbal therapies are free from side effects and toxicity, unlike allopathic medicines. Studies on hepatoprotective herbs will contribute to the

benefit of the populations needing herbal treatment for both diseases without involving the use of synthetic drugs and reducing the side effects of synthetic drugs.

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